

Complexity and Competitiveness: Analyzing Knowledge Production's Impact on Productivity in European Metropolitan Regions

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1. Introduction

The uneven economic development that can be observed across countries and regions is often attributed to productivity differences that allow some countries or regions to flourish while others remain uncompetitive (Nelson and Winter, 1977; Prescott, 1998; Hall and Jones, 1999; Beugelsdijk, Klasing and Milionis, 2018). While numerous characteristics of the economy drive these productivity differences (Porter, 1990; Scott and Storper, 2003; Rodríguez-Pose, 2013; Rodríguez-Pose and Di Cataldo, 2015), technological progress enabled by new knowledge is often considered the most essential factor for productivity gains and economic growth. Consequently, in the fields of regional science and economic geography, the unequal economic development of countries, regions, and cities is linked to the uneven spatial distribution of knowledge production (Malecki, 1991; Glaeser *et al.*, 1992; Feldman, 1994). In order to support regions in their long-term economic development and to reduce disparities between regions, European policy makers implement innovation policies.

Smart specialization strategies (S3) in Europe, highly funded by the EU's cohesion policies, have garnered attention in different academic circles, notably Economic Geography. Initially praised for their tailored approach to regional innovation, S3 faced early challenges, particularly in operationalizing goals and targets due to the complexity of regional factors. Balland *et al.* (2019) proposed an empirical framework to guide S3, advising regions to focus on innovating within accessible but complex knowledge fields or technologies. The argument is made that focusing on complex knowledge is more beneficial from an economic perspective. This is because complex knowledge is expected to be more difficult to imitate and less likely to be diffused to other (competitor) regions (Balland and Rigby, 2017; Balland *et al.*, 2020; van der Wouden, 2020; Pintar and Scherngell, 2022). So, recent studies have repeatedly called to integrate the concept of *knowledge complexity* into regional innovation policy, particularly into S3 (see e.g., Sbardella, Perruchas, *et al.*, 2018; Balland and Boschma, 2019; Balland *et al.*, 2019; Pugliese *et al.*, 2019; Sbardella *et al.*, 2021, 2022; Balland, 2022; Li and Rigby, 2022; Mewes and Broekel, 2022; Rigby *et al.*, 2022; Barbieri *et al.*, 2023).

While we support the conceptual calls, we identify lingering questions that must be addressed to substantiate claims about the positive impacts of complex knowledge. Firstly, existing studies often overlook productivity when assessing the economic effects of complex knowledge, focusing solely on income or output changes. Given the importance of productivity for sustainable growth, exploring the relationship between complex knowledge and productivity is essential. Secondly, defining complexity poses a challenge, with various interpretations existing in literature. Addressing this issue requires either advocating for a specific definition or incorporating multiple perspectives into analysis. In this paper, we use the

latter approach and combine sensible versions of the three most popular measures of knowledge complexity in the field (for a review, see Pintar and Essletzbichler, 2022).

Despite the positive competition effect of producing complex knowledge, we can observe a notable trend that innovating firms are increasingly relying on external knowledge sources to supplement or replace local capabilities (Bathelt, Malmberg and Maskell, 2004; Breschi and Lenzi, 2015; Van der Wouden and Rigby, 2019; van der Wouden, 2020; Balland and Boschma, 2021). This collaboration often takes place in formal R&D collaboration networks (Fritsch and Franke, 2004; Scherngell, 2013). However, given the difficulty in transferring and effectively utilizing knowledge (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990), it remains uncertain if regions can harness inter-regional spillovers of complex knowledge to boost productivity.

This study aims to address these unresolved issues by examining the impact of complex knowledge production on the prospective growth of total factor productivity (TFP) in European metropolitan regions. The empirical investigation utilizes economic and patent data in a balanced panel of 192 city-regions across Europe spanning from 1996 to 2021. To adequately consider the inter-regional spillovers inherent in innovative activities, a spatial econometric modeling approach is adopted. This method not only controls for latent and potentially confounding spatial effects within a regression framework but also allows an estimation of the extent to which city-regions might accrue benefits from fostering closer collaborations with neighboring regions.

2. Theoretical framework and model

Enterprises engage in innovation, notably research and development (R&D), for a myriad of motives. On one hand, successful R&D initiatives are often imperative for a company's competitiveness and survival, as underscored by Schumpeter (1942) and Aghion and Howitt (1992). Conversely, profit-oriented firms are incentivized to innovate, aiming either to enhance product quality without inflating costs or to streamline production expenses through novel techniques or technological advancements (Grossman and Helpman, 1991). Despite firms' aspirations to exclusively reap the benefits of their innovation endeavors, the non-rivalrous nature and partial excludability of knowledge facilitate its diffusion, enabling other enterprises to capitalize on it as well (Romer, 1986, 1990; Audretsch and Feldman, 1996; Foray, 2004). These knowledge spillovers occupy a central theme across various academic domains, spanning Economics of Innovation, Regional Science, and Economic Geography, among others, albeit with distinct disciplinary perspectives. In addition to other explanatory factors such as regional institutions and physical resource endowments, positive external effects resulting from knowledge spillovers in agglomerations (cities) are frequently cited as drivers of sustained regional growth (Glaeser *et al.*, 1992; Fujita and Thisse, 1996). Consequently, regional knowledge production, bolstered within cities or smaller agglomerations by favorable spillover effects, which are conducive either within similar industries (Marshall, 1890; Arrow, 1962; Romer, 1986) or facilitated by urban diversity and the cross-pollination of ideas across industries (Jacobs, 1969), can explain the uneven distribution of economic performance (Malecki, 1991; Feldman, 1994).

This article refrains from reviewing the extensive literature exploring the diverse effects of knowledge across various settings, be it at different levels of analysis (firms, industries, regions, nations) or in different model specifications. Numerous reviews (Griliches, 1986; Mairesse and Sassenou, 1991; Döring and Schnellenbach, 2006; Hall, Mairesse and Mohnen, 2010; Hall, 2011; Lööf, Mairesse and Mohnen, 2017; Ugur and Vivarelli, 2021) provide comprehensive

overviews in this regard. Suffice it to say, abundant research demonstrates the positive impact of technological change resulting from innovation and knowledge production on economic growth through productivity enhancements. Noteworthy studies illustrate this relationship at various levels such as firm-level analyses (Griliches and Mairesse, 1984; Griliches, 1986; Adams and Jaffe, 1994; Mairesse, Mohnen and Kremp, 2005; Griffith *et al.*, 2006; Hall, Lotti and Mairesse, 2009; Raymond *et al.*, 2015), industry productivity development (Scherer, 1982; Griliches and Lichtenberg, 1984; Pakes and Schankerman, 1984), national perspectives (Coe and Helpman, 1995; Park, 1995; Coe, Helpman and Hoffmaister, 2009), and regional analyses (Fischer, Scherngell and Reismann, 2009; Quatraro, 2009, 2010; Antonelli, Patrucco and Quatraro, 2011; Dettori, Marrocu and Paci, 2012; Marrocu, Paci and Usai, 2013, 2022; Scherngell, Borowiecki and Hu, 2014; Capello and Lenzi, 2015; Wanzenböck, 2017). Regional-level investigations often focus separately on determinants of knowledge production and its impact on productivity increases. In light of the wealth of studies highlighting the pivotal role of knowledge production in economic development, policymakers, especially at the regional level, often turn to innovation policies. However, while most studies have traditionally analyzed the quantity of knowledge only, typically measured by R&D expenditures or patent counts, it is crucial to acknowledge that not all knowledge holds equal value (Foray, 2004). Knowledge that can be easily replicated and diffused across geographical space may offer diminished economic benefits in the medium to long term for firms or regions that develop it.

Recent studies within Economic Geography and related fields have embraced these ideas under the concept of *knowledge complexity*, employing network science and system approaches to gauge the quality of knowledge produced (Sorenson, Rivkin and Fleming, 2006; Balland and Rigby, 2017). In essence, high-quality economic knowledge is often tacit, challenging to codify and transfer (Polanyi, 1958, 1966; Kogut and Zander, 1992; Gertler, 2003). Kogut and Zander (1993) link knowledge complexity to its “tacitness”, suggesting that complex knowledge is particularly reliant on learning and experiences that resist codification. Given the abstract nature of tacit knowledge, empirical measurements of economic or knowledge complexity typically rely on indirect methods. Numerous studies approximate complexity by assessing the difficulty of integrating knowledge components or by examining the geographical distribution of knowledge production (Fleming and Sorenson, 2001; Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009; Tacchella *et al.*, 2012; Broekel, 2019; Pugliese *et al.*, 2019). Regions that consistently produce valuable, complex knowledge signal the presence of necessary regional capabilities (Hidalgo, 2021; Balland *et al.*, 2022). While related studies have shown that complex knowledge is both unequally distributed in space (Balland and Rigby, 2017; Balland *et al.*, 2020; Pintar and Scherngell, 2022), less likely to diffuse over long distances (Sorenson, 2005; van der Wouden, 2020) and associated with future economic growth (Sbardella, Pugliese, *et al.*, 2018; Li and Rigby, 2022; Mewes and Broekel, 2022; Rigby *et al.*, 2022), direct evidence of the productivity increasing effects of complex versus non-complex knowledge is underdeveloped (Antonelli, Crespi and Quatraro, 2022).

The main purpose of this article is to investigate whether regional specialization in complex knowledge fields, as opposed to indiscriminate knowledge production, positively impacts future economic productivity. Additionally, we explore two underexplored questions in the empirical literature on regional knowledge complexity. Firstly, we examine whether regions benefit from geographical proximity to others engaged in knowledge production, particularly in complex fields, thereby investigating evidence of inter-regional knowledge spillovers affecting regional productivity development. Secondly, we inquire into the temporal dynamics of the effect of knowledge production on productivity. Specifically, we investigate whether

significant productivity effects require a minimum number of years to materialize and whether there is a linear progression in these effects over time.

This paper focuses on the downstream efficiency effects of knowledge on economic output. To explore the connection between regional knowledge and total factor productivity (TFP), we utilize a spatial econometric modeling framework to account for the interconnectivity of subnational regions in both innovation and economic production. Building on the *knowledge capital model* introduced by Griliches (1979), our approach extends the conventional Cobb-Douglas production function by incorporating (complex) knowledge capital as an additional input factor. This framework, widely adopted across various fields, underscores the role of knowledge in enhancing productivity at different levels of analysis (for reviews, see e.g., Mairesse and Sassenou, 1991; Hall, Mairesse and Mohnen, 2010; Ugur and Vivarelli, 2021). Following Scherngell et al. (2014), we further extend the model by allowing regions to benefit from region-external complex and non-complex knowledge which leads to equation (1).

$$Q_{it} = Ae^{\lambda t} C_{it}^{\alpha} L_{it}^{\beta} K_{it}^{\gamma_1} \tilde{K}_{it}^{\gamma_2} cK_{it}^{\gamma_3} \tilde{cK}_{it}^{\gamma_4} e^{u_{it}} \quad (1)$$

Here, Q_{it} represents the real output of region i during period t , typically gross value added. C_{it} denotes the deflated physical capital stock, while L_{it} represents the labor supply, usually adjusted for factors like working hours. These variables are conventional factors of production. The knowledge capital stock (K_{it}) has historically been constructed by aggregating R&D investments over a specific timeframe leading up to t . Nowadays, modern studies often approximate knowledge capital using patent output. The term $Ae^{\lambda t}$ serves as a proxy for technological progress, encompassing a rate of disembodied technological change (λ). The term $e^{u_{it}}$ accounts for all unmeasured factors influencing regional output. The exponents α , β , and γ denote the elasticities of production with respect to physical capital, labor supply, and knowledge capital. Assuming constant returns to scale and diminishing marginal returns of conventional production factors, $\alpha + \beta = 1$. However, the elasticity of production concerning knowledge capital is not inherently constrained, as knowledge may exhibit increasing returns to scale. Further, cK_{it} represents complex knowledge capital, while the tilde (\sim) signifies the region-external variant of knowledge and complex knowledge capital. Taking logs of equation (1) and applying the *accounting approach* to TFP calculation (Schatzer *et al.*, 2019), equals equation (2) below where lower case letters refer to logged values.

$$tfp_{it} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} q_{it} - \alpha c_{it} - \beta l_{it} = \gamma_1 k_{it} + \gamma_2 \tilde{k}_{it} + \gamma_3 ck_{it} + \gamma_4 \tilde{c}k_{it} + \lambda_t + u_{it} \quad (2)$$

Recent studies within the field have often shifted attention from the level of TFP to studying the growth of total factor productivity (Männasoo, Hein and Ruubel, 2018; Siller *et al.*, 2021; Marrocu, Paci and Usai, 2022). This emphasis on growth is justified because highly efficient regions, despite having high total factor productivity, do not always also exhibit high TFP growth rates. Conversely, some Eastern European regions have demonstrated substantial TFP growth despite starting from low overall productivity levels (Siller *et al.*, 2021; Marrocu, Paci and Usai, 2022). Understanding the type of knowledge that drives this convergence effect is therefore crucial for policy considerations, particularly in the context of the EU's cohesion policy. Thus, this paper specifically focuses on explaining regional TFP growth, instead of studying the level of regional TFP.

Reformulating equation (2) for TFP growth as well as bringing it in conventional notation for spatial modelling, yields:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}_t = \rho \mathbf{W}(\kappa) \Delta \mathbf{p}_t + \theta \mathbf{p}_t + \gamma_1 \mathbf{k}_t + \gamma_2 \mathbf{W}(\kappa) \mathbf{k}_t + \gamma_3 \mathbf{c} \mathbf{k}_t + \gamma_4 \mathbf{W}(\kappa) \mathbf{c} \mathbf{k}_t + \phi \lambda_t + \epsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where $\Delta \mathbf{p}_t$ now refers to the vector of regional TFP growth rates from period t to some year in the future (which we will vary). Now, the spatial weight matrix $\rho \mathbf{W}(\kappa)$ ¹ that connects each region with its neighbor is used to spatially lag both the dependent variable and all knowledge capital variables. In line with convention, ρ represents the coefficient of the spatial autoregressive progress between neighboring regions. Importantly, this formulation enables the TFP growth of neighboring regions to directly impact the TFP growth of the regions themselves. Time-fixed effects are represented by ϕ . Finally, ϵ_t denotes an independent and identically distributed (iid) error term. Equation (3) represents a common spatial econometric model specification, the *spatial Durbin model* (SDM). Following related literature, we estimate the model using maximum likelihood, see LeSage and Pace (2009) or Elhorst (2014) for details.

3. Data

In accordance with existing research, we utilize patent data as a proxy for regional knowledge generation. Specifically, we obtain patent applications submitted to the European Patent Office (EPO) by inventors residing in EU and EFTA countries from 2000 to 2017, sourced from the OECD REGPAT database (see Maraut *et al.*, 2008). This database links patents to NUTS-3 regions based on inventor residence. We then associate patents located in these NUTS-3 regions with metropolitan regions defined by EUROSTAT², excluding patents from peripheral regions with minimal patent activity. For more information, refer to Pintar and Scherngell (2022). These metropolitan regions more accurately reflect functional economic areas, combining NUTS-3 regions in a manner that better represents urban regions and approximates the functional regions of cities, including commuter zones surrounding urban centers.

Knowledge capital (k) is calculated as the cumulative sum of regional patent applications over a five-year period. As mentioned in the first two sections of this paper, there exists a wide variety in different empirical approaches to approximate regional knowledge complexity. Utilizing an agnostic approach, we use a combination of three sensible and popular measures³ to weight regional knowledge capital (Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009; Tacchella *et al.*, 2012; Broekel, 2019). The complexity weight that is used is equal to the geometric mean of normalized complexity scores⁴.

¹ Depending on κ which we also vary in the estimation of different models. Specifically, we use eight different κ -nearest neighbor spatial weight matrices, ranging from three to 10 nearest neighbors. In other words, each region is directly connected to the same number of nearest neighbors. See LeSage and Pace (2009) for details on spatial econometric techniques.

² See https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Territorial_typologies_manual_-_metropolitan_regions.

³ According to the comprehensive comparison and review of alternative knowledge complexity measures by Pintar and Essletzbichler (2022).

⁴ Specifically, we use the variation number 1 of the *economic complexity index* (Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009), number 25 of the *economic fitness complexity index* (Tacchella *et al.*, 2012) and variation number 41 of the *structural diversity index* (Broekel, 2019) listed in Pintar and Essletzbichler (2022).

To calculate regional TFP values as in equation (2), we set $\alpha = 1/3$ and $\beta = 2/3$, following related literature (Beugelsdijk, Klasing and Milionis, 2018). Regional output (q) is measured by real regional gross value added. Labor input (l) is equal to the the number of employees, adjusted for variations in average working hours across countries. The capital stock of a region is calculated as the cumulative sum of past real gross fixed capital formation (investment) over a five-year period. All non-patent variables mentioned are obtained from ARDECO⁵.

4. Preliminary results

Figure 1 summarizes the results regarding the main research question of this paper. What effect does complex knowledge capital, in contrast to non-complex knowledge capital, have on future TFP growth. By varying the number of years in the future the average yearly growth rate (dependent variable) is calculated as well as the number of κ -nearest neighbors that are included in the modelling via spatial spillover effects, the results can be set into context. The coefficient estimates of spatial models that include a spatial lag of the dependent variable (like our model in equation (3)) cannot be directly interpreted. Instead, it is usual to construct from the model output *direct*, *indirect* and *total* impact estimates (LeSage and Pace, 2009). Direct impacts then can be understood similarly to coefficient estimates of the standard linear model, i.e., as marginal effects. However, as the model includes global spillovers, cross-region spillovers that end up at the focal region again, are included in the estimate as well. Indirect impact estimates can be interpreted as the cross-regional spillover effect while total impacts are the sum of the two aforementioned impact estimates. Total impact estimates can be understood as the total effect on the whole system of regions that is brought about by the change in the independent variable. For details see, for example LeSage and Pace (2009) or Elhorst (2014).

Overall, we can see that the total effect of increasing complex knowledge capital leads to a significant increase in regional future productivity growth. This is the case for almost all variations of the model. Interestingly, we can observe a somewhat non-linear effect where in the very short-term we cannot find a significant effect on TFP growth, we then see an effect in the medium term which is then again reduced to about zero after around 13 years. A similar pattern can be shown for direct and indirect impacts as well. However, it seems that regions can actually benefit from producing complex knowledge themselves for a markedly longer period than if they relied on region-external knowledge to boost their economy. While it seems that regions may be able to utilize spillover effects of complex knowledge and translate them to economic productivity increases, this is not true for all configurations of TFP growth and neighborhood structure. As already mentioned, positive spillover effects tend to be mostly short-lived. On the other hand, if regions are directly connected to a wider system of regions (more than 7 nearest neighbors are included), rewards seem to be higher. Note that these impact estimates are always to be interpreted holding non-complex knowledge capital constant. Thus, complex knowledge capital offers a differential positive TFP growth effect, other than merely increasing innovation efforts indiscriminately.

⁵ ARDECO, which stands for the Annual Regional Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Regional and Urban Policy, provides comprehensive regional data. You can find more information about it at https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/territorial/ardeco-database_en. To relate TFP growth with various knowledge capital measures, we must also standardize economic variables to the European metropolitan region level. While GVA data and employment figures are already available at the NUTS 3 level, gross fixed capital formation (investment) is only accessible at the NUTS 2 level. To address this, we allocate investment data to NUTS 3 regions based on population data and then aggregate it to the desired metropolitan regions.

Figure 1. Impact estimates of complex knowledge capital

Note: The figure above summarizes impact estimates for complex knowledge capital of all variations of the regression equation (3). While in this figure only impacts related to complex knowledge capital are displayed, results are based on the full model

including all covariates in equation (3). The model is run for each version of average yearly TFP growth (from one to 15 years into the future). Similarly, the models vary the κ -nearest spatial weight matrix from three to the 10 nearest neighbors. Points refer to the value of the impact estimate and whiskers display the confidence interval (95%) around it. If the line extends over the dotted vertical line (0), the impact estimate can be considered significantly different from zero. Results for other covariates are available upon request.

5. Conclusion and limitations

This study explores the association between knowledge capital, particularly complex knowledge capital, and future TFP growth. Employing an extended regional KCM framework inspired by Scherngell et al. (2014), we introduce the notion of knowledge complexity to enhance traditional measures of knowledge production. While our findings are preliminary, they suggest that complex knowledge capital exhibits a distinct and promising relationship with regional TFP growth in the future. Regions can benefit from focusing on complex knowledge production themselves or strengthen their embeddedness with surrounding regions to reap the benefits of complex knowledge. However, it seems that relying purely on spillover effects is not a long-term strategy.

In this study, our analysis was constrained by the available data, particularly the somewhat outdated patent data. In future research, we plan to explore the feasibility of incorporating more recent patent data into our framework. Additionally, we aim to enhance our modeling approach by employing alternative neighborhood definitions (such as social distance etc.) and conducting a range of robustness tests.

Author contributions

Nico Pintar: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing . Thomas Scherngell: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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